

INVESTIGATION ABOUT TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

Tsuyoshi Matsuo¹ and Kazuro Kageyama²

¹School of Engineering, The University of Tokyo
7-3-1 Hongo, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo, Japan

Email: matsuo@sys.t.u-tokyo.ac.jp, web page: <http://www.t.u-tokyo.ac.jp>

²School of Engineering, The University of Tokyo
7-3-1 Hongo, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo, Japan

Email: kageyama@giso.t.u-tokyo.ac.jp, web page: <http://www.t.u-tokyo.ac.jp>

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ABSTRACT

The unidirectional compressive strength of fiber reinforced plastics is dominantly influenced by plastic kinking process which is caused by any initial local fiber misalignment and fiber-directional shear deformation. Compressive strength in the fiber direction is much less than tensile strength and plays a significant role for designing some robust materials and structures.

Above all, carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite laminate, particularly compressive molded by pressing machine and using versatile resin, assumes an effective role in high speed molding process. On the other hand, its compressive strength depends a great deal on the temperature-dependent elastic-plastic behavior of the matrix.

In this study, a new compressive test method using specimen with waisted gauge section for unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites was proposed and confirmed to be capable of evaluating its compressive strength in fiber direction and failure mode with high reliability. In addition, it was theoretically verified that the elastic-plastic shear property in out-of-plane direction has a direct correlation with the compressive strength by a proposed modified Budiansky's solution considering some defined elastic and plastic parameters obtained from the experimental shear result as well as kink band angle and initial fiber misalignment in laminated direction. These aspects also suggest that the viscoelastic plasticity of the matrix resin determines the temperature-dependent compressive strength in fiber direction of unidirectional composites. So, a novel test method using specimen with waisted gauge section was applied to a series of temperature-dependent compressive tests, and their compressive failure modes were investigated. It was indicated that the proposed modified Budiansky's solution has a certain availability to establish the relationship between the compressive strength and the out-of-plane shear property of unidirectional thermoplastic composites at any different temperature.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite material (thermoplastic CFRP) whose matrix is a universally prevalent and comparatively low-cost plastics like polypropylene or polyamide has been expected to be applied to various engineering products including automobiles and airplanes because of its high mechanical and lightweight properties about the same as thermosetting CFRP [1]. In case of polypropylene, the interfacial adhesive strength between carbon fiber and matrix resin is necessary to be improved by some important technologies including acid-modification of resin [2].

In the process from material to product as a representative of vehicle structural member, a pre-consolidated plate of thermoplastic CFRP like a bulk of GMT or SMC is heated up to over resin-melting temperature in a infrared heater, and right after that, the heated plate is delivered to and placed in a mold heated up under resin-solidification temperature set on a press machine, and automatically

cooled down and compressive pressed by a pressing machine [3]. By utilizing such a molding process, a 3D-shape structural member filling up the cavity of mold is obtained at a fast speed available for continuous production system.

However, polypropylene generally has a demerit of low thermal resistance comparing to the other resin. In addition, in spite of the fact that fiber reinforced composite materials display a noteworthy performance in fiber-directional tensile strength, compressive strength in fiber direction is much less than tensile strength. The difference of strength in tensile and compressive direction frequently makes it difficult and complex to design fiber orientation of products. These characteristics induce some concerns about considerable quality degradation especially in high temperature. So, it is required to reveal a compressive failure mechanism in fiber direction of thermoplastic CFRP depending on temperature and explain its failure behavior by some theoretical model.

This study, using unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced polypropylene, focuses on the kink band failure mechanism caused by shear and transverse stress in fiber direction under external compressive load. It is explained that the buckling failure is initiated by fiber misalignment and caused by kink band rotation in conjunction with fiber-directional shear deformation [4]. According to the mechanism, the compressive strength in fiber direction dominantly depends on the matrix elastic-plastic behavior, in other words indicates a strong correlation with temperature. For this verification, the compressive test method using a specimen form with in-plane waisted gauge section was proposed. The method was able to generate a certain kink band failure within a gauge area and evaluate the proper compressive strength. And, a kink band failure model based on Budiansky's solution was applied to explanation of the relationship between the compressive strength and the elastic-plastic shear stress-strain property in fiber direction at any different temperature condition.

2 THEORETICAL MODEL FOR COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH

Based on the kink band model shown in Fig. 1, the formula for compressive strength proposed by Budiansky and Fleck [4] is following as below.

$$\frac{\sigma_c}{G} = \frac{\alpha^2}{1 + n \cdot k^{1/n} \cdot \left(\alpha \cdot \frac{\phi_0 / \gamma_Y}{n-1} \right)^{\frac{n-1}{n}}} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{here, } \alpha = \sqrt{1 + \frac{E_T}{G} \cdot \tan^2 \beta} \quad (2)$$

This equation defines ϕ_0 as initial fiber misalignment angle, ϕ as rotated angle of kink band and β as kink band failure angle, adopting the equilibrium of force in kink band section where σ_T as shear stress and τ as transverse tensile stress are generated by fiber rotation under σ^∞ as external compressive stress, and then enables to calculate σ_c as unidirectional compressive strength by using the other parameters of G as shear modulus in fiber direction, E_T as tensile modulus in fiber-transverse direction, k and n as strain-hardening coefficient values in elastic-plastic shear property and γ_Y as yield shear strain in fiber direction.

Figure 1: Kink band model.

In addition, in order to make this formula more effective, the authors transformed the calculating formula into more practical equation adopting some plastic parameters obtained by applying Ramberg-Osgood relationship as the following expression to the experimental shear strain-stress curve in fiber direction.

$$\gamma = \frac{\tau}{G} \cdot \left[1 + k \cdot \left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_Y} \right)^{n-1} \right] \quad (3)$$

The strain-hardening parameter n can be evaluated uniquely by fitting the above relationship to an experimental shear strain-stress curve. And, defining shear strain and stress of an arbitrary point on the strain-stress curve as γ_i and σ_i respectively and assigning a relation of $\gamma_Y = \tau_Y / G$ to the equation (1), it can be transformed to the following formula.

$$\sigma_c = \frac{G \cdot \alpha^2}{1 + n \cdot \left(\alpha \cdot \frac{G \cdot \phi_0}{n-1} \right)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} \cdot \frac{(G \cdot \gamma_i - \tau_i)^{\frac{1}{n}}}{\tau_i}} \quad (4)$$

This equation means that an experimental shear stress-strain property which is expressed by shear modulus, shear strain-hardening value and measurement strain-stress values of an arbitrary point on the curve leads to a compressive strength in fiber direction, only if obtaining initial fiber misalignment angle, tensile modulus in transverse direction and kink band angle.

3 SPMECIMEN AND EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

This chapter explains the specimen manufacturing process, the evaluating method for fiber misalignment angle and kink band angle, and the verifying methods for shear strain-stress property and compressive strength in fiber direction.

3.1 Specimen manufacturing

In the heating and cooling process, several tapes of continuous-fiber prepreg which is manufactured by impregnating a bundle of carbon fiber (TR50 by Mitsubishi Rayon) with acid-modified polypropylene (by TOYOBO) are laminated, heated up in mold and compressive pressed in a hot-press machine (by PINETTE EMIDECAU INDUSTRIES). After that, a consolidated unidirectional CF/PP laminate is demolded and obtained. The schematic illustration of the molding process is shown in Fig. 2. The size of cross-section of laminated test specimen is 15 mm with width and about 2 mm with thickness.

3.2 Observation and evaluation of inside of specimen by 3D X-ray CT

Initial fiber misalignment angle before compressive failure and kink band angle after compressive failure can be quantitatively detected by non-destructive observation of inside of specimen by using 3D X-ray CT (by Yamato Scientific Co., Ltd.) which makes it possible to display a picture of an arbitrary cross-section of specimen.

Figure 2: Molding process of unidirectional CF/PP laminate.

3.3 Shear test in fiber direction under several temperatures

Mentioned above, shear strain-stress parameters, G , n and a set of γ_i and σ_i at a defined temperature have to be obtained experimentally and assigned into the equation (4) in order to predict the compressive strength at the same temperature.

The test method for shear property in fiber direction needs a $[+45/-45]_{6S}$ laminated plate manufactured from unidirectional prepreg tape mentioned in section 3.1 in the same hot-pressing process. The test specimen is tensile-loaded in longitudinal direction which is oriented at an angle of 45 degree with respect to fiber direction as shown in Fig. 3. The specimen and the upper and lower grips connected to the hydraulic servo testing machine (by MTS) are set in the thermostatic chamber which can accurately control the temperature around the test specimen.

Shear strain in fiber direction can be obtained from the difference between two values measured by two strain gauges, parallel to and perpendicular to the tensile axis respectively. On the other hand, shear stress can be obtained as a half of calculated tensile stress of the measured load divided by cross-sectional area. And, these result in experimental shear strain-stress curves under a series of defined temperatures, -30°C , 0°C , 25°C , 50°C and 80°C .

Figure 3: Shear test of CF/PP laminate and thermostatic chamber.

Figure 4: Test specimen geometry.

Figure 5: Test specimen and setting in grips.

3.4 Compressive test in fiber direction at several temperatures

This study proposed a novel compressive test method, which uses a unidirectional composite laminate with waisted gauge section whose figure is shown in Fig. 4. The waisted specimen is cut from a laminate manufactured through the molding process shown in Fig. 2. The compressive test under the same temperature condition as each shear test, -30°C , 0°C , 25°C , 50°C or 80°C , is performed in the same loading system as shear test in section 3.3, in which the hydraulic upper and lower grips hold the gripping areas of the test specimen in Fig. 4. The actual test specimen and holding situation are indicated in Fig. 5. Compressive strain during test is measured by two strain gauges bonded to both sides of specimen, so that buckling failure or misalignment between test specimen and loading axis may be detected under compressive loading. Compressive stress is evaluated by dividing the measured load by cross-sectional area of waisted gauge section of test specimen. These test procedure leads to a set of compressive strain-stress curves by both strain gauges under every temperature condition. The tests are stopped right after compressive failure, and the compressive strength under each temperature is evaluated from the maximum stress on the strain-stress curve.

4 TEST RESULTS AND INVESTIGATION

This chapter shows the test results about fiber misalignment angle, shear properties under defined temperatures and compressive strengths with observation of kink band failure under the corresponding temperatures, and also investigate the validation of the above theoretical calculation model for compressive strength.

4.1 Initial fiber misalignment

The initial fiber misalignment angle was confirmed quantitatively by observation of the inside of specimen before failure as explained in section 3.2. Fig. 6 shows a few images of in-plane and out-of-plane cross section by 3D X-ray CT. The comparison of fibers straightness accuracy between the in-plane and out-of-plane cross-section indicates that the fiber waviness is larger in out-of-plane direction than in in-plane direction. This assumes that the fiber waviness may be caused by high pressure in laminating direction during hot-pressing process. In Fig. 6 (right), the magnified pictures of the out-of-plane cross-section where a larger fiber waviness is detected indicates that the maximum fiber misalignment is potentially defined as 3.2° by virtual angle measurement function equipped with the CT system.

Figure 6: CT images of inside of test specimen (left) and magnified pictures focusing on fiber waviness in out-of-plane direction (right).

Figure 7: Shear properties under defined temperatures.

Detected parameters	Temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]				
	(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	(e)
	- 30	0	25	50	80
Shear modulus, G [GPa]	3.9	3.0	1.5	1.0	0.54
Hardening coefficient, n	5.0	4.3	3.7	3.5	3.3

Table 1: Shear parameters from experimental result at each temperature.

4.2 Shear test result and evaluation of shear parameters

Shear strain-stress curves under some defined temperatures, -30°C , 0°C , 25°C , 50°C and 80°C , were obtained as shown in Fig. 7, which indicates the horizontal axis as shear strain and the vertical axis as shear stress. From these curves, the shear properties are definitely dependent on temperature. In every case of temperature condition, shear modulus G evaluated from a slope ranging from 0.1 % to 0.3 % strain and strain-hardening coefficient n evaluated from degradation of a slope after yield are listed in Table 1. The value of n is obtained from the curve fitting into the equation (3).

4.3 Compressive test result and kink band angle

A novel compressive test method enables to detect a compressive strength with high accuracy at every temperature, generating kink band failure in the waisted gauge section as expected without buckling. Fig. 8 shows strain stress curves under defined temperatures and comparison of compressive strength among different temperatures, in which the error bar means a range between the maximum and the minimum values among three test results at each temperature. No buckling causes the strain-stress curves measured by two strain gauges on both sides at each temperature to indicate a similar tendency. And, it was verified that the compressive strength has a clear temperature dependence.

An example of kink band failure after compressive test under 25°C is shown in Fig. 9. In case of 25°C , the inside observation by 3D X-ray CT with measurement function for geometry of image determines the kink band angle as about 30° . Similarly, in the other cases of temperature, the kink band angles were estimated respectively, around 20° at -30°C , 25° to 30° at 0°C , around 30° at 25°C , around 30° at 50°C and around 30° at 80°C .

Figure 8: Strain-stress curves at various temperatures - (a) -30°C (b) 0°C (c) 25°C (d) 50°C (e) 80°C and compressive strength at every temperature.

Figure 9: Kink band failure by 3D X-ray CT.

Figure 10: Predicted temperature-dependent compressive strength to kink band angle.

Figure 11: Comparison of compressive strengths predicted by theoretical model and obtained from novel experimental method.

4.4 Relationship between compressive strength and shear property

The detected shear parameters from the shear test results and analysis as Table 1 shows enable to predict the temperature-dependent unidirectional compressive strength as a function of kink band angle, assuming that every initial fiber misalignment angle equals to 3.0° in all temperature conditions. Such temperature-dependent relationships from utilizing the equation (4) are indicated in Fig. 10, whose horizontal axis means kink band angle and vertical axis means predicted compressive strength. In addition to the same graph, a predicted range of kink band angle through all temperature conditions can be expressed as a gray area based on the experimental results obtained from compressive test and CT measurement mentioned in section 4.3. These analytical procedures find out the relationship of compressive strength dependent on temperature as Fig. 11 indicates. And at the same time, it is obvious that the theoretical predicted range of compressive strength fit with the experimental values plotted as circle signals at every temperature resulting from section 4.3. It follows that the prediction model based on kink band failure which leads to the equation (4) was validated and experimentally-demonstrated for understanding the compressive failure mechanism of unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites.

5 CONCLUSION

This study, by using thermoplastic CFRP which uses polypropylene as matrix resin, focused on the unidirectional compressive strength and investigated about the influence of temperature-dependent shear property in fiber direction. For the validation of strong correlation between compressive strength

and the elastic-plastic shear property in out-of-plane direction, the theoretical model based on kink band failure was introduced and experimentally verified by a proposed compressive test method. For more detail, it followed that:

1. A proposed compressive test method using a test specimen with waisted gauge section was available for generating the kink band failure in out-of-plane direction and evaluating the accurate compressive strength for unidirectional CF/PP laminate at every defined temperature from -30°C to 80°C.
2. The theoretical equation for compressive strength based on kink band model was modified by taking into consideration that the experimentally-obtained nonlinear shear strain-stress curve at any temperature condition fits with the Ramberg-Osgood relationship which express elastic-plastic relationship with strain-hardening coefficient.
3. The observation of inside of test specimen by 3D X-ray CT could quantify the actual angle of initial fiber misalignment before failure and kink band after failure, aiming at assigning these geometric factors to the above-mentioned equation.
4. These geometric factors and the temperature-dependent elastic-plastic shear parameters obtained from tensile test for +45/-45 laminated specimen were applicable for the predicted calculation of compressive strength. And, it was confirmed that the theoretical prediction was well accorded with the experimental results for temperature-dependent compressive strength.

For these aspects, it can result in a precise understanding that unidirectional compressive strength of thermoplastic CFRP is strongly influenced by fiber-directional shear property, which indicates a clear temperature-dependent elastic-plastic behavior especially in case of polypropylene.

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REFERENCES

- [1] U.K. Vaidya and K.K. Chawla, Processing of fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites, *International Materials Reviews*, **53**, 2008, pp. 185-218.
- [2] T. Hayashi, A. Sasaki, T. Terasawa and K. Akiyama, Study on interfacial adhesion between carbon fiber thermoplastic resin and mechanical properties of the composite, *Proceedings of the 11th Japan International SAMPE Symposium & Exhibition, Tokyo, Japan, November 25-26, 2009*.
- [3] T. Matsuo, K. Takayama, J. Takahashi, S. Nagoh, K. Kiriyama and T. Hayashi, Design and manufacture of anisotropic hollow beam using thermoplastic composites, *Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Composite Materials, Montreal, Canada, July 28-August 2, 2013*.
- [4] B. Budiansky and N.A. Fleck, Compressive failure of fibre composites, *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, **41**, 1993, pp. 183-211.